

WB, siRNA treated
Ref. to Fig 1B, 3D

WB, shRNA induction with dox
Ref. to Fig 1B, 3D

agarose gels
Ref. to Fig 1C-E, G

Ref. to Fig. 2C

Ref. to Fig. 2E

Ref. to Fig. 2G

Ref. to Fig. 2G

Ref. to Fig. 3G, H

Ref. to Fig. 3F, I

Ref. to Fig. 4C

Atp2a1 e22 minigenes:

Ref. to Fig. 4E

MBNL1 e5 minigene (Mbnl1,2 DKO MEF background)

Ref. to Fig. 4F

MBNL1 e5 minigene:

Ref. to Fig. 4G

Ref. to Fig. 4H

Supplementary Figure 8

Ref. to Fig. 5A

Ref. to Fig. 5B, C

Ref. to Fig. 5E

Supplementary Figure 8

Ref. to Suppl. Fig. S1

Ref. to Suppl. Fig. S2E

Ref. to Suppl. Fig. S3B

